

Approach to Water Tariffing

Guidelines for authorities to implement adequate water pricing and tariff structure needed to ensure the financial feasibility of the water treatment and reclamation infrastructure

Introduction: In drought-prone mediterranean regions like Southern Spain, current water use is not sustainable, and reclaimed water use not economically attractive given farmers have access to well and groundwater use at a low cost or even [free of charge](#). An appropriate water tariff structure could be introduced to create incentive and finance associated water treatment and reclamation costs, particularly in countries where all surface and ground waters are in the public domain and controlled by the regional government. In this context, a water tariff structure can be defined as a fair charge imposed on wastewater operators to cover the costs of providing the water service whilst ensuring that it is affordable ([WAREG](#)).

Areas of Local and Regional Authority Action:

- a. **Transition to reclaimed water as the primary option for irrigation**, at least in highly stressed drought-affected areas.
 - A shift towards wastewater reuse as the primary option for irrigators could be enacted via a requirement in the local or regional Comprehensive Water Reuse Plan. To streamline new EU legislative requirements, this plan could be aligned with Reclaimed Water Risk Management Plans (Royal Decree 1085/2024), now mandatory. To ensure these plans are actionable on the ground, authorities should additionally work towards ensuring all municipalities have adequate urban wastewater treatment systems for reuse (in particular many small municipalities lack the tertiary treatment required for wastewater reclamation).
- b. **Enact water demand management** ([EEA Report](#), p.78)
 - A tariff structure which encourages efficient water use and reduces wasteful usage should be established. A one-size-fits-all high tariff would push regional farmers to grow more high monetary value, water-intensive crops like avocados. Instead, the tariff must also encourage reclaimed water use by farmers of less water-intensive crops to reduce overall agricultural water needs in the region.
- c. Establish **Strong Integrated Governance** between Water Providers and Water Users.
 - There is a need to govern reclaimed water use beyond community-led initiatives (e.g. Comunidades de Regantes, Spain), to establish a supportive framework at the regional level. Without clearly defined roles and responsibilities and an understanding of both provider and user needs, reclaimed water can go unused. For example in Murcia, Spain, one particular year the Los Alcázares and San Javier treatment plants generated around 90% reclaimed water, but only 40% of that was used in agriculture due to a mismatch in need (P2Green workshop's participant, January 2025). Use of reclaimed water can be further supported by authorities through related policies, such as farming or tourism where public authorities have a strong influence over water consumption.
- d. **Establish a public database on where and how much water is being used across the region.**
 - Data on how much water and wastewater is available and reclaimed where is necessary to establish sustainable reuse. The recent Water Reuse Regulations require local governments to ask for data as part of the risk management plan – this data collection opportunity can be used to set up a publicly available data base.
- e. **Build appropriate distribution Infrastructure.**

- Appropriate networks are needed to allocate reclaimed water across entire regions. For example, in the case of La Axarquía, Spain, wastewater treatment plants are located on the coast in the municipality; however, the irrigation communities are distributed throughout the entire region (also inland) and there is no distribution pipe network to facilitate the use of that resource. Infrastructure should be designed to minimise the number of pumping stations required to move the reclaimed water. Further, appropriate planning can be used to improve distribution, with reclaimed water users being located closer to each other, leading to relevant savings in infrastructure and transport costs (Hermanowicz *et al.* 2001).
- f. **Streamline Water Reuse Permitting Procedure** ([IWA paper](#))
- Speed up reclaimed water use license approval processing time. A streamlining of the process of approval can ensure appropriate consideration of risks in a reasonable timeframe for water users. A broader range of opportunities for reuse should also be considered to scale-up the demand for reclaimed water, for example reuse in industry. Mixing treated wastewater with conventional freshwater sources (e.g. groundwater, surface), can help reduce costs and increase water quality (mainly to reduce salinity) (e.g. Rincón de La Victoria WWTP-WRP). Roquetas, Spain, for example, has been granted a concession that began in 2016 and as of March 2025 has not been operational.

Aspects to keep into account when establishing a sustainable and fair water tariff structure:

- It should be established in line with the **polluter pays principle**, whilst also accounting for treatment and plant investment costs that have already been assumed by public administration (i.e. public taxes).
- **Cover the pure and hard costs** (e.g. treatment, transportation, storage).
- Consider not only fixed costs and variable costs, but also **seasonal costs**, since farmers do not always use this water.
- Create a tariff system that considers not only the principle of cost recovery, but also the **principle of equity** – considering and accounting for farmers not producing high-cost crops that could not otherwise afford using reclaimed water. This avoids only high-water intensity crops dominating the region.
- **Incentivise and reward sustainable farming practices**. For instance, lower tariffs for farmers that adopt sustainable practices:
 - those who use less fertilisers or pesticides,
 - those who have a smaller water footprint, and
 - those who contribute to [recharge aquifers](#)